

DIDACTIC OPPORTUNITIES FOR DEVELOPING REFLEXIVE SKILLS

Usmanaliyeva Orzigul

Methodologist at the Pedagogical Skills Center of Andijan Region, Researcher

Abstract: Within the framework of the formative assessment approach широко being introduced into the education system, the necessity of evaluating not only the learner's level of knowledge but also their emotional attitudes, values, and practical skills in an integrated manner is substantiated. Additionally, based on the taxonomy of educational objectives proposed by B. Bloom, the content of the three domains of learning, their interconnection, and their importance in the educational process are highlighted. The results of the study are significant in that formative assessment serves to develop learners comprehensively.

Keywords: Formative assessment, taxonomy, cognitive domain, reflexive domain, psychomotor domain, learning outcomes, motivation, primary education. The cognitive, reflexive, and psychomotor domains of education, which serve to comprehensively develop learners' knowledge, skills, and attitudes, are of particular importance. In recent years, the formative assessment approach being introduced into the education system specifically предусматривает evaluating these three domains in an integrated manner. In the process of formative assessment, not only the learner's level of knowledge is analyzed, but also their emotional attitudes, values, and practical skills are regularly examined.

The first of the three domains of learning is cognitive skills. Cognitive competence is based on six intellectual abilities developed by psychologist Benjamin Bloom and his colleagues. This concept is known as "Bloom's Taxonomy." In practice, Bloom's Taxonomy serves as a kind of navigator, enabling teachers to effectively organize lessons, apply appropriate tasks and assessment tools

for each stage of learning, and anticipate the necessary learning outcomes from students. Each competence is expressed through action verbs that describe how learners can apply what they have learned during the lesson, and it serves as a tool for teachers to transform students' responses to tasks into learning outcomes.

“**Taxonomy**” refers to the principle of arranging something in a hierarchical order (from lower to higher levels). This system of higher educational objectives was developed by scientists at the University of Chicago under the leadership of American psychologist **Benjamin Bloom** [4].

Each domain requires its own specific pedagogical tasks, teaching methods, and assessment criteria, and serves to ensure that learners can function successfully in real-life situations. These domains are closely interconnected and complement one another.

Bloom's Taxonomy includes the following intellectual skills:

- **Remembering** – the ability to recall or recognize previously learned information. At this stage, a learner may write down, list, or name information.
- **Understanding** – the ability to comprehend or interpret information based on previously learned material. At this stage, learners express their understanding by explaining, summarizing, or describing information.
- **Applying** – the stage of independently solving tasks or problems, where the learner selects and uses appropriate information relevant to a given situation.
- **Analyzing** – the process of understanding or evaluating questions and assumptions in order to draw conclusions. At this stage, learners are expected to compare, contrast, and analyze information.
- **Evaluating** – the process of assessing information or sources based on

e

- **Creating** – the ability to generate new ideas or plans based on existing information. At this stage, learners are expected to create, design, invent, and develop.

Bloom's Taxonomy can be applied in any subject area, taking into account learners' age characteristics. For primary school students, it is recommended to focus on the first three stages—remembering, understanding, and applying—and to expect learning outcomes accordingly [3].

- **Receiving** – involves the passive awareness of emotions and feelings. At this initial stage, learners must achieve success in order to progress further. For example, a learner waits for others to finish speaking, asks for necessary information, selects, clarifies, and uses it.
- **Responding** – the learner actively participates in a process and reacts to it. In demonstrating learning outcomes, the learner may show compliance, willingness to respond, or satisfaction (motivation). For example, they participate in class discussions, give presentations, help peers, or answer questions about a book they have read.
- **Valuing** – refers to the worth or value a person assigns to a particular phenomenon or behavior. It is based on internalizing a set of values, which become evident in the learner's observable behavior. For example, a learner demonstrates problem-solving skills, proposes and responsibly follows a plan of action, or writes an essay on a social issue and defends their position.
- **Organizing** – involves comparing different values, resolving conflicts between them, and prioritizing. The focus is on comparing, relating, and analyzing values. Learners understand the need for balance between freedom

and responsibility and take accountability for their actions. They develop systematic plans for solving problems and manage their time effectively to meet school, family, and personal needs. For example, a student who aims to be on the honor roll understands that preparing for exams is more important than going to the cinema with friends.

Characterization (Internalization) – this refers to a value system that controls behavior, where the learner acts in accordance with values they have developed and accepted. Educational objectives are linked to the learner’s overall adaptation patterns (personal, social, emotional). For example, a learner demonstrates confidence when working independently, collaborates in group activities (teamwork), approaches problem-solving objectively, revises decisions, and adjusts behavior based on new evidence. They value people not for their appearance but for who they are. The learner recognizes that cheating is unethical and, even if a friend suggests copying answers, strives to complete a difficult task independently.

Guided Response – learners often begin acquiring complex skills through imitation, trial and error, or by following instructions. For example, a learner experiments with different methods of measuring a certain volume of a chemical substance, solves a mathematical equation as demonstrated, sketches a model design, or learns to construct a simple diagram by watching a related video.

Mechanism – learners develop basic proficiency in performing complex tasks through practice. For example, they accurately draw a right triangle, tell time correctly about 70% of the time, independently use a personal computer, repair a leaking faucet, or confidently perform a piece assigned by a teacher after several weeks of piano practice.

Complex Overt Response – learners acquire the ability to perform highly skilled tasks. This stage is characterized by proficiency, speed, high accuracy, and minimal energy expenditure. For example, a learner can play a piece on the piano without looking at the keys or operate a computer quickly and accurately.

Adaptation – learners further develop their skills and can modify them to meet specific requirements. For example, they respond effectively to unexpected situations, adjust instructions to meet learners' needs, or a culinary student modifies a recipe according to dietary restrictions [6].

Assessment of the **cognitive domain** serves to determine learners' abilities to acquire knowledge, analyze, compare, generalize, and apply it in problem situations. This process develops critical and logical thinking in learners and helps strengthen their knowledge [1]. At the same time, the results of cognitive assessment enable teachers to adapt the educational process and improve instructional materials based on an individual approach.

Assessment of the **reflexive domain** plays an important role in identifying learners' attitudes toward education, motivation, values, and socio-emotional state. Neglecting this domain may reduce the effectiveness of the educational process, as positive emotional attitudes and intrinsic motivation are key factors in the conscious and sustainable acquisition of knowledge. Through formative assessment, regular monitoring of changes in the reflexive domain contributes to the development of self-assessment, responsibility, and reflection skills in learners.

Assessment of the **psychomotor domain** makes it possible to evaluate learners' practical actions, skills, and competencies. This domain is especially important in experimental, practical, and professionally oriented educational contexts. Psychomotor assessment helps determine the extent to which learners can apply

theoretical knowledge in practice, as well as the accuracy and independence with which they perform technical actions. As a result, a solid foundation is created for the development of learners' life and professional competencies.

From this perspective, the integrated assessment of cognitive, reflexive, and psychomotor domains creates a developmental learning environment. Such an approach contributes to effective planning of pedagogical activities, in-depth analysis of learners' achievement levels, and sustainable improvement of educational outcomes. In conclusion, the integration of these three domains through formative assessment is one of the key priorities of modern education, and its systematic implementation in practice elevates the quality of education to a new level.

References

1. Bloom, B. S. (1956). *Taxonomy of Educational Objectives: The Classification of Educational Goals*. New York: Longmans, Green.
2. Anderson, L. W., & Krathwohl, D. R. (2001). *A Taxonomy for Learning, Teaching, and Assessing: A Revision of Bloom's Taxonomy of Educational Objectives*. New York: Longman.
3. Black, P., & Wiliam, D. (1998). *Assessment and Classroom Learning*. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 5(1), 7–74.
4. Harlen, W. (2007). *Assessment of Learning*. London: Sage Publications.
5. Krathwohl, D. R. (2002). *A Revision of Bloom's Taxonomy: An Overview*. *Theory Into Practice*, 41(4), 212–218.